

Examining Marketing Variables as Predictors of Patronage of Insurance Products among Academic Staff in Lagos State Universities

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Abstract

Insurance remains a critical instrument for financial risk management and economic stability, yet its penetration in Nigeria continues to lag behind global and regional averages. Despite reforms and awareness campaigns, subscription rates remain low, raising questions about the determinants of patronage among educated professionals. Guided by the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), this study examined how cost perception, regulatory issues, and socio-economic factors influence the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in Lagos State universities. The study employed a descriptive survey design, targeting 1,695 academic staff across the University of Lagos, Lagos State University, and Caleb University, with 1,261 valid responses (74% response rate) obtained through total enumeration. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire validated via a pilot study (Cronbach's alpha > 0.70) and analyzed with descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and ANOVA. Findings revealed that academic staff generally held a positive perception of insurance costs, indicating affordability was not a barrier to patronage. Regulatory issues were not perceived as significant constraints, as respondents disagreed that compulsory

insurance or regulatory concerns shaped their subscription behaviour. However, income level emerged as a significant moderating factor, influencing the relationship between perceived cost and patronage ($\Delta R^2 = 0.002$, $p < 0.05$). Despite positive cost perceptions, respondents reported low patronage of education, motor, and life insurance products offered by leading companies such as AIICO, AXA Mansard, and Cornerstone. This suggests that while affordability and regulation are not primary deterrents, socio-economic realities—particular. The study concludes that insurance patronage among academic staff is more strongly determined by income-related considerations than by cost or regulatory concerns. It recommends that insurance providers adopt income-sensitive strategies, such as flexible premium structures and tailored product offerings, to enhance uptake among professionals. By addressing socio-economic constraints and improving perceived value, insurers can strengthen trust, expand coverage, and contribute to greater financial security in Nigeria's academic sector.

Keywords: Cost perception, Regulatory issues, Income level, Insurance patronage, Academic staff

Introduction

The insurance industry plays a critical role in financial intermediation, risk management, and economic stability. By providing mechanisms for pooling and transferring risks, insurance contributes to social security, business confidence, and sustainable development (Akinlo, 2019). However, in Nigeria, the sector has continued to struggle with poor penetration and limited patronage compared to other emerging economies. According to Statista (2024), insurance penetration in Nigeria was only 0.37% of GDP in 2022, far below the 12% recorded in the United States and below the African average. This under-performance raises concerns about the underlying factors limiting the growth of insurance patronage in the country.

Several factors have been identified as barriers to insurance adoption in Nigeria. Cost perception remains a major determinant, as many individuals perceive insurance products as expensive or unaffordable relative to their disposable income (Dansu et al., 2018). Misconceptions about premium payments and lack of perceived value further discourage uptake. Similarly, regulatory issues such as weak enforcement of compulsory insurance schemes, delays in claims settlement, and inadequate consumer protection mechanisms have been shown to undermine public confidence (Okonkwo, 2020). At the same time, socio-economic factors such as income disparities, education levels, religious and cultural attitudes, and general economic instability shape consumer attitudes toward insurance products (Ajemunigbohun et al., 2020; Fofie, 2016).

The persistence of these challenges indicates that insurance patronage in Nigeria is not only a financial issue but also a matter of perception, institutional credibility, and socio-cultural alignment. In environments where economic resources are constrained, the decision to purchase insurance is weighed against competing priorities such as food, education, and housing. Thus, individuals who view insurance as a discretionary or luxury expense are less likely to adopt it, regardless of its potential long-term benefits.

Despite recent reforms such as recapitalisation, digitalisation of services, and awareness campaigns, insurance penetration remains low, suggesting that cost-related concerns, regulatory weaknesses, and socio-economic constraints continue to act as significant impediments to

patronage (Nwoji, 2023). Academic staff of universities constitute a consumer segment that is particularly important for examining these issues. With relatively stable incomes, higher educational attainment, and exposure to financial products, they possess the capacity to engage with insurance services in ways that may differ from the general population.

Against this backdrop, the present study examines the extent to which cost perception, regulatory issues, and socio-economic factors predict patronage of insurance products among academic staff in selected Nigerian universities.

Statement of Problem

Patronage of insurance products in Nigeria has remained relatively low despite the recognised importance of insurance in providing financial protection, security, and stability. Several challenges have been consistently highlighted in the extant literature, including poor premium payment, delays or outright absence of claims settlement, lack of trust among the insuring public, and a weak regulatory framework (Fofie, 2016). While insurance brands are generally associated with stability, trust, and protection against risk in many economies, in Nigeria, the opposite perception persists. This has limited the ability of the sector to gain wider acceptance, even though insurance provides critical support in times of loss.

Scholars have argued that the low patronage of insurance in Nigeria is not only linked to inefficiencies within the industry but also to broader socio-cultural and economic issues. Ajemunigbohun (2017) observed that preconceived notions about financial service companies limit efforts to build strong brand equity in the insurance market. Similarly, Dansu et al. (2018) noted that cultural beliefs and religious leanings influence individuals' willingness to adopt insurance products. In addition, the absence of transparency in policy structures and poor claims payment history has been reported to reduce confidence in the industry (Fofie, 2016). These persistent issues have contributed to low insurance penetration, with gross written premium representing just 1.8% of Nigeria's GDP in 2021 (GlobalData, 2022).

More importantly, questions remain as to why even relatively educated and economically active groups, such as university academics, may still demonstrate low levels of insurance patronage. Prior studies have shown that awareness of the value of insurance is often limited, even among educated Nigerians (Ajemunigbohun, 2020).

While numerous studies have examined customer perception of insurance, brand preference, determinants of purchase decisions, and levels of awareness across different demographic groups (Lawal et al., 2021; Adamu, 2018), there is a paucity of research that focuses specifically on academics as a unique consumer segment. Based on the foregoing, this study seeks to examine the extent to which cost perception, regulatory issues, and socio-economic factors influence the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in selected Nigerian universities.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to investigate how cost perception, regulatory issues, and socio-economic factors predict the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in Nigerian universities. The specific objectives are to:

1. Ascertain the perception of the cost of insurance products among academic staff in Nigerian universities.

2. Examine how regulatory issues affect the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in Nigerian universities.
3. Determine the influence of socio-economic factors on the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in Nigerian universities.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: Perceived cost has no significant influence on the patronage of insurance products among academic staff of Nigerian universities.

H₀₂: Regulatory issues have no significant effect on the patronage of insurance products among academic staff of Nigerian universities.

H₀₃: Income level has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between brand equity and patronage of insurance companies products among academic staff of select universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Cost and Insurance companies' Products Patronage

Buying decisions are influenced by multiple factors, one of the most critical being the cost of the product. The cost of any product is often shaped by operational expenses and the cost of production inputs, which in turn determine whether the product is affordable or not. Affordability plays a pivotal role in consumer decision-making because, as Martin et al. (2019) note, a product that is reasonably priced will not be too costly for individuals of limited means to purchase. In this regard, organisations usually adopt pricing strategies that balance competitiveness, affordability, and a sustainable rate of return on investment.

In the context of insurance, cost is primarily reflected in the premium charged for coverage. Chmielowiec-Lewczuk (2019) describes this as the amount paid by policyholders for the acquisition of insurance products, which is not only shaped by technical factors but also by human elements such as customer expectations and their willingness to engage with insurance services. This is significant because consumers often weigh factors such as affordability, perceived quality, and the expected benefits of the product before making purchase decisions.

Prabhakar et al. (2018) further distinguish between direct costs which are those clearly visible to the policyholder, such as the stated premium, and indirect costs, which are less obvious and may be associated with hidden charges, delays in claims settlement, or opportunity costs of engaging with insurance. Both categories of costs jointly influence consumer behaviour. In Nigeria, particularly, the burden of indirect costs has been found to heighten public apathy towards insurance patronage and has contributed to negative perceptions of insurance as a viable financial product.

Regulatory Concerns and Insurance Companies' Products Patronage

The Nigerian insurance industry is primarily regulated by the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM), which oversees compliance through the Insurance Act and a range of guidelines addressing market conduct, prudential standards, and solvency requirements. In recent years, NAICOM has introduced several reforms such as the Bancassurance Guidelines (2017) and the

Microinsurance Guidelines (2018), aimed at expanding access and deepening insurance penetration. In addition to NAICOM's regulations, other relevant legislation includes compulsory insurance provisions, local content laws in the oil and gas sector, and policies governing the National Health Insurance Scheme.

Despite these regulatory frameworks, the insurance market continues to grapple with significant challenges. A large number of insurers operate with relatively small balance sheets and weak business fundamentals, leading to inefficiencies within the sector. Expense ratios are often high, while claims ratios tend to be either too low to deliver meaningful consumer value or too high to sustain profitability. These dynamics raise solvency concerns for many operators, prompting NAICOM to implement measures such as the 2018 Tier-Based Minimum Solvency Capital requirements in an effort to consolidate the market (Cenfri, 2018).

Beyond solvency and prudential regulation, NAICOM has also sought to strengthen consumer protection. Such measures are particularly important in contexts of information asymmetry and low financial literacy, where consumers may lack adequate understanding of insurance contracts and the claims process. Nevertheless, regulatory efforts have not fully addressed persistent challenges such as low awareness, limited trust in insurers, and the prevalence of moral hazard and adverse selection. Moreover, the Nigerian economy continues to face a shortage of critical expertise in the insurance sector, including underwriting, actuarial science, and general insurance business skills, further constraining industry growth.

Taken together, these issues highlight that while regulatory reforms have been introduced to promote stability, consumer protection, and market expansion, weaknesses in enforcement, limited awareness, and structural skill deficits continue to hinder the ability of regulation to stimulate increased patronage of insurance products in Nigeria.

Income and Insurance Companies' Products Patronage

Income levels remain one of the most critical socio-economic determinants of insurance consumption. Daniel (2012) observes that individuals in the low-income bracket of the Nigerian economy are particularly vulnerable to risks such as illness, death, accidents, and property damage. In the absence of adequate government-provided safety nets, these risks often result in devastating financial consequences. This situation creates a potential window of opportunity for micro-insurance products that are specifically designed to provide affordable risk protection for low-income households.

In contrast, in many developed economies, insurance is widely regarded as an essential component of the financial and social structure. Certain forms of insurance, such as health, motor vehicle, or liability insurance, are made compulsory by law, thereby ensuring widespread coverage. In such contexts, the role of insurance in protecting against shocks is well established, particularly among poorer households who face heightened vulnerability to risks and possess fewer resources to recover from major financial losses (Dansu, Abass & Oyetayo, 2018).

In Nigeria, however, the situation is markedly different. Patronage of insurance products remains disproportionately low among both low- and middle-income earners, with affordability emerging as a key barrier. Insurance premiums are often perceived as high relative to disposable income, making them less attractive to households already struggling with competing financial priorities such as food, education, and housing. This challenge is further compounded by the informal nature

of much of Nigeria's economy, where irregular income streams limit the ability of individuals to make consistent premium payments.

Also, the relationship between income and insurance patronage is not merely about affordability, but also about perceived value. Many low-income households view insurance as a luxury rather than a necessity, partly due to limited awareness and lack of trust in insurers. This perception reduces willingness to sacrifice scarce income for future, uncertain benefits. On the other hand, for middle- and higher-income groups, although affordability is less of an issue, scepticism about claims settlement and dissatisfaction with service delivery still hinder broader uptake.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Planned Behaviour

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), proposed by Icek Ajzen in 1985, is a widely recognized psychological framework for understanding and predicting human Behaviour (Abdulkareem et al., 2020). The theory posits that an individual's intention to perform a Behaviour is the most immediate and reliable predictor of actual Behaviour (Ogiemwonyi, 2020). In essence, intention reflects a person's readiness and willingness to engage in a particular action, shaped by personal beliefs, social influences, and perceived control over the Behaviour.

TPB identifies three core determinants of Behavioural intention. The first is attitude, which represents an individual's positive or negative evaluation of performing the Behaviour (Otache, 2020). For instance, in the context of insurance, if academic staff perceive insurance products as beneficial, reliable, and fairly priced, they are more likely to form a favourable attitude toward subscribing to them.

The second determinant is subjective norms, which refer to perceived social pressure to perform or abstain from the Behaviour (Osman et al., 2016). Social influences from colleagues, family, or professional networks may shape the decision to patronize insurance products, especially in communities where peer and societal expectations are strong.

The third determinant is perceived Behavioural control, which captures an individual's assessment of their ability to perform the Behaviour (Acheampong & Tweneboah-Koduah, 2017). In the insurance context, this could include confidence in affording premiums, understanding policy terms, and accessing services easily. High perceived control increases the likelihood that intention will translate into actual patronage.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour is relevant to this study as it provides a clear framework to understand how academic staff's attitudes, social influences, and perceived control shape their intention to patronize insurance products, which in turn affects their actual purchasing behaviour.

Review of Empirical Studies

Garba et al. (2011), for instance, investigated the factors affecting insurance patronage in Borno State, Nigeria, using a survey of 400 residents. The study revealed that low trust in insurers, limited education, low income, and lack of knowledge about insurance services significantly constrained patronage. While informative, the reliance on quota sampling limits the generalisability of the findings.

Similarly, Fofie (2016) explored the influence of socio-economic and demographic factors on insurance patronage in Ghana. Using a sample of 200 respondents and Probit regression analysis, the study found that income, education, and transparency of insurance policies significantly affect subscription decisions, while religion had little effect. The research highlighted that indirect costs, limited understanding of policies, and inadequate claims processes also impede patronage.

In Nigeria, Dansu et al. (2018) focused on Third-Party Liability (TPL) motor insurance among academic staff in Lagos State. Through survey and factor analysis, the study revealed that family size, vehicle ownership, price, and marital status significantly influenced the choice of TPL policies. Findings suggested that affordability and practical considerations were central to purchase decisions, highlighting the intersection of socio-economic factors and insurance uptake.

Ali (2016) examined the determinants of Islamic Takaful insurance acceptance in Mogadishu, Somalia. Using survey data from 179 respondents, the study identified awareness, attitude, perception, and knowledge as key predictors of insurance adoption. The results highlighted the role of informational and perceptual factors in shaping insurance behaviours.

Marafa et al. (2019) investigated public awareness and perception of insurance companies in Enugu State, Nigeria, using 400 survey respondents. Results indicated low public awareness and a poor image of insurance firms, which contributed to limited patronage. This study emphasized the critical role of perception and trust in the insurance sector.

Enitilo (2017) evaluated the effect of promotional activities on insurance patronage in Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. Findings from 373 respondents demonstrated that media advertising, personal selling, and sales promotion positively influenced patronage, suggesting that strategic communication and marketing are essential in encouraging uptake.

Lawal and Ashurov (2021) examined factors influencing the acceptance and awareness of Takaful insurance in Nigeria. Surveying 205 respondents across multiple states, the study found that service quality, attitude, awareness, and perceived behavioural control significantly affected acceptance. However, many respondents lacked sufficient information to differentiate conventional from Islamic insurance products, highlighting the persistent knowledge gap in the sector.

Collectively, these studies reveal that socio-economic factors, awareness, perception, marketing strategies, and trust are critical determinants of insurance patronage. However, a gap remains in understanding how cost perception, regulatory frameworks, and broader socio-economic factors interact to shape the insurance behaviours of educated professionals such as academic staff in Nigerian universities. This study seeks to bridge this gap by examining the influence of these factors on the patronage of top insurance companies' products in Lagos State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine how cost perception, regulatory issues, and socio-economic factors influence the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in Lagos State universities. The population comprised all academic staff in the state's universities, with one institution selected from each category: University of Lagos (813 staff), Lagos State University (798 staff), and Caleb University (84 staff), giving a total of 1,695 staff. Using total enumeration, all academic staff in the selected universities were included as respondents. The study focused on four prominent insurance companies in Nigeria, AIICO, AXA

Mansard, and Cornerstone, whose products were examined to assess how cost perception, regulatory issues, and socio-economic factors influence patronage. These companies were selected due to their established presence, extensive product offerings, significant market share. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire aligned with the study objectives, and a pilot study with 60 academic staff from Babcock University confirmed reliability, with Cronbach’s alpha coefficients above 0.70. Data collection lasted six weeks, employing nine trained research assistants and both physical and online questionnaires. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS, with descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations) summarizing responses and regression analysis and ANOVA used to test hypotheses and examine the influence of cost perception, regulatory concerns, and socio-economic factors on insurance product patronage. Ethical standards were observed, ensuring confidentiality, voluntary participation, and academic use of the data.

Results

A total of 1,261 responses were successfully retrieved from the sampled academic staff, representing a 74% response rate. The analysis that follows is based on these returned questionnaires.

Research Objective 1: Ascertain the perception of the cost of insurance products among academic staff in Nigerian universities.

Table 1: Perception of the Cost of Insurance Products among Academic Staff

Statements	SA Freq. (%)	A Freq. (%)	D Freq. (%)	SD Freq. (%)	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation (SD)
The cost of life insurance policy of my insurance company is expensive	197 (15.6)	342 (27.1)	370 (29.3)	352 (27.9)	2.30	1.04
The general insurance product of my insurance company is expensive	119 (9.4)	429 (34)	412 (32.7)	301 (23.9)	2.29	0.93
The motor insurance policy of my insurance company is expensive	163 (12.9)	344 (27.3)	411 (32.6)	342 (27.2)	2.26	1.00
The cost of insurance product affects my patronage of my insurance company	105 (8.3)	405 (32.1)	387 (30.7)	364 (28.9)	2.20	0.95
Average Overall Mean					2.26	0.98

Source: Field Survey 2024

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree ***Decision Rule if mean is 1 to 1.74=Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 =Agree; 3.25 to 4= Strongly Agree. *Note: SA+A= Negative Perception; D+SD= Positive Perception*

Table 1 shows that academic staff of selected universities had positive perception of the cost of insurance products (\bar{x} =2.26). This was the case because they disagreed with the following, that the: cost of life insurance policy of their insurance company was expensive (\bar{x} =2.30), general insurance product of their insurance company was expensive (\bar{x} =2.29), the motor insurance policy of their insurance company was expensive (\bar{x} =2.26) and that the cost of insurance product affected their patronage of their insurance company (\bar{x} =2.20). This suggests that academic staff of selected universities had positive perception of the cost of insurance products because they did not perceive

the cost of life insurance policy, general insurance product and the motor insurance policy of their insurance company to be expensive.

Research Objective 2: Examine how regulatory issues affect the patronage of insurance products among academic staff in Nigerian universities.

Table 2: Showing Regulatory Issues affecting patronage of Insurance Companies’ Products among Academic Staff

Statements	SA Freq. (%)	A Freq. (%)	D Freq. (%)	SD Freq. (%)	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation (SD)
I patronise only compulsory insurance products	152 (12.1)	444 (35.2)	378 (30)	287 (22.8)	2.37	0.96
My patronage of life assurance products is made easy by regulatory concerns	182 (14.4)	368 (29.2)	363 (28.8)	348 (27.6)	2.30	1.03
Regulatory concerns makes my patronage of insurance products difficult	106 (8.4)	434 (34.4)	374 (29.7)	347 (27.5)	2.24	0.95
Regulatory concerns affect my patronage of insurance products	160 (12.7)	354 (28.1)	345 (27.4)	402 (31.9)	2.22	1.03
Average Overall Mean					2.28	0.99

Source: Field Survey 2024

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree *Decision Rule if mean is 1 to 1.74=Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 =Agree; 3.25 to 4= Strongly Agree**

Table 2 depicts that academic staff of selected universities disagreed they had concerns about regulatory issues in patronising insurance companies’ products (\bar{x} =2.28). They did not have concerns about regulatory issues in respect of not: patronising only compulsory insurance products (\bar{x} =2.37), patronising life insurance because it was made easy by regulatory concerns (\bar{x} =2.30) and not being affected by regulatory concerns while patronising insurance products (\bar{x} =2.22). This suggests that academic staff of selected universities did not have concerns about regulatory issues insurance companies’ products. This was the case because they were not patronising insurance products because they were made compulsory; they were not patronising life insurance because it was made easy by regulatory concerns and they were not being affected by regulatory issues while patronising insurance companies’ products.

Test of Hypotheses

Decision Rule

The following rules guided the application of simple and multiple linear regression for this study. If the p-value, which is the probability value, was less or equal to 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected; if p value was greater than 0.05, the hypothesis was accepted.

H₀₁: Perceived cost has no significant influence on the patronage of insurance products among academic staff of Nigerian universities.

Table 3: Moderating Effect of Cost on the Relationship between Brand Equity and Patronage of Insurance Companies' Products

Model	Coeff.	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	0.784	0.520	1.508	0.132	-0.236	1.805
Brand Equity	0.130	0.011	11.555	0.000	0.108	0.152
Cost	0.081	0.064	1.264	0.206	-0.045	0.208
Moderating Effect of Cost	0.001	0.001	1.124	0.261	-0.001	0.003
	R ² -Chng	F	df1	df2	P	
Moderating Effect of Cost	0.000	1.264	1	1257	0.261	
	Effect	SE	t	p		

Source: Field Survey 2024

Key: *LLCI* = Lower Level Confidence Interval; *ULCI* = Upper Level Confidence Interval

Table 3 indicates that cost has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between brand equity and patronage of insurance companies' products among academic staff of select universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\Delta R^2 = 0.000$, $B = 0.001$, $t = 1.124$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Ho2: Regulatory issues have no significant effect on the patronage of insurance products among academic staff of Nigerian universities.

Table 4: Moderating Effect of Regulatory Issues the Relationship between Brand Equity and Patronage of Insurance Companies' Products

Model	Coeff.	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	0.288	0.532	0.541	0.589	-0.756	1.331
Brand Equity	0.123	0.013	9.869	0.000	0.099	0.148
Regulatory Concern	0.255	0.062	3.636	0.000	0.103	0.346
Moderating Effect of Regulatory Concern	0.000	0.001	0.226	0.821	-0.002	0.002
	R ² -Chng	F	df1	df2	P	
Moderating Effect of Regulatory Concern	0.000	0.051	1	1257	0.821	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Key: *LLCI* = Lower Level Confidence Interval; *ULCI* = Upper Level Confidence Interval

Table 4 indicates that regulatory issues have no significant moderating effect on the relationship between brand equity and patronage of insurance companies' products among academic staff of select universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\Delta R^2 = 0.000$, $B = 0.000$, $t = 0.226$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

H03: Income level has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between brand equity and patronage of insurance companies products among academic staff of select universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Moderating Effect of Income Level on the Relationship between Brand Equity and Patronage of Insurance Companies’ Products

Model	Coeff.	SE	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.552	0.369	4.210	0.000	0.829	2.276
Brand Equity	0.146	0.007	21.588	0.000	0.133	0.159
Income Level	-0.565	0.169	-3.339	0.001	-0.897	-0.233
Moderating Effect of Income Level	0.009	0.003	2.776	0.006	0.003	0.016

	R ² -Chng	F	df1	df2	P
Moderating Effect of Income Level	0.002	7.705	1	1257	0.006

	Effect	SE	t	p
Low Income Level	0.155	0.004	35.445	0.000
High Income Level	0.174	0.006	29.966	0.000

Source: Field Survey 2024

Key: LLCI = Lower Level Confidence Interval; ULCI = Upper Level Confidence Interval

Table 5 indicates that income level has a positive significant moderating effect of the relationship between brand equity and patronage of insurance companies’ products among academic staff of select universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\Delta R^2 = 0.002$, $B = 0.009$, $t = 2.776$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. In addition, the analysis shows that the level of income resulted in 0.2 percent change in R square ($\Delta R^2 = 0.002$). The analysis further indicates that low-income level ($B = 0.155$, $t = 35.445$, $p < 0.05$) and high-income level ($B = 0.174$, $t = 29.966$, $p < 0.05$) positively significantly moderated the relationship between brand equity and patronage of insurance companies’ products among academic staff of select universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. This implies that low- and high-income level among academic staff in selected universities in Lagos State, Nigeria improve how brand equity influences patronage of insurance companies’ products.

Discussion of Findings

The first objective of this study was to examine academic staff perceptions of the cost of insurance products. Findings revealed that respondents generally perceived the cost of life insurance, general insurance, and motor insurance products as reasonable, indicating a positive perception of affordability. This suggests that cost is not a major barrier to patronage among academic staff in the selected universities. The finding aligns with Khurram et al. (2018), who also reported that price consciousness did not significantly moderate the relationship between brand factors and insurance adoption.

The second objective explored whether regulatory concerns influenced the patronage of insurance products. Results indicated that regulatory issues had no significant impact on subscription decisions. Academic staff were not influenced by compulsion or regulatory facilitation in their decision to patronize insurance products, suggesting that the regulatory environment alone is insufficient to drive uptake. This reinforces the view that awareness, trust, and product knowledge remain critical in motivating insurance adoption (Marafa et al., 2019; Enitilo, 2017).

The study further investigated the moderating role of socio-economic factors, particularly income, in shaping the relationship between insurance perceptions and patronage. Analysis showed that income level had a positive and significant moderating effect ($\Delta R^2 = 0.002$, $B = 0.009$, $t = 2.776$, $p < 0.05$), with both low and high-income respondents showing stronger patronage tendencies when brand and product attributes were favourable. This suggests that disposable income, irrespective of the level, enhances the influence of insurance attributes on subscription decisions. These findings are consistent with Fofie (2016) and Garba et al. (2011), who highlighted income as a critical determinant of insurance uptake in Ghana and Nigeria, respectively.

Overall, the study confirms that while cost and regulatory factors are perceived positively or neutral, socio-economic conditions like income play a more decisive role in influencing insurance patronage.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that academic staff in selected universities in Lagos State generally perceive the cost of insurance products as reasonable and do not hold significant regulatory concerns regarding insurance patronage. However, income level emerged as a critical socio-economic factor that positively influences subscription behaviour. This indicates that while affordability and regulatory compliance are not major barriers, financial capacity plays a significant role in determining patronage of insurance products.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Insurance companies should intensify efforts to build strong brand awareness through targeted communication campaigns within universities, ensuring academic staff are well-informed about available products and benefits.
- Insurers should align their products with the specific needs and values of academic staff to increase relevance and appeal.
- Companies should promote closer relationships with clients through seminars, partnerships, and campus-based outreach programs, reinforcing trust and engagement.
- Insurers should enhance service delivery, ensure transparency in policies, and promote prompt claims settlement to build confidence and encourage higher patronage.

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